

Mental Fatigue Detection from ECG Data Using Active Machine Learning with a Query-by-Committee Strategy

Arthur Coelho Bastos
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0007-5619-1925

Patrick Alves Carneiro
Faculty of Electrical Engineering
Federal University of Uberlândia
Uberlândia, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0001-0960-2003

Luís Miguel Machado Lopes Macedo
Department of Informatics Engineering
University of Coimbra
Coimbra, Portugal
ORCID: 0000-0002-3144-0362

Abstract— This study explores the use of Active Machine Learning (AL) in the identification of mental fatigue from heart rate variability (HRV) data extracted from electrocardiograms (ECG). Based on the support vector machine (SVM) classifier, which demonstrated the best predictive performance in the reference study, we applied AL with the Query by Committee (QBC) strategy. This approach utilized a committee of models, including SVM, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), and Random Forest, to identify informative samples, significantly reducing the need for large volumes of labeled data. The method was evaluated with data collected during cognitive task performance and resting periods, considering time windows of 3, 4, and 5 minutes and batches of unlabeled data of sizes 20, 40, and 60. With a batch size of 20 and a 5-minute window, the model achieved an AUC of 0.837 and an accuracy of 75%, results comparable to those obtained in the reference study. This work demonstrates that AL is an effective strategy for optimizing mental fatigue classification, even in resource-constrained scenarios, enabling high-quality results with reduced datasets.

Keywords — Strategy, Model, Dataset, Fatigue and Classifier

I. INTRODUCTION

Mental Fatigue (MF) is characterized by feelings of tiredness and exhaustion, accompanied by a reduction in motivation to sustain effort, as well as mood changes and slower information processing speed [1–3]. In the workplace, the lack of control over MF is associated with negative impacts on productivity, an increased number of medical leaves, and absenteeism, harming companies reputations and leading to significant economic costs [4].

According to [5], work shifts exceeding 12.5 hours are associated with a higher risk of reduced vigilance, an increase in medical errors, and occupational accidents. Trainee doctors working more than 24 hours experience double the attention lapses and 36% more serious medical errors compared to those working 16-hour shifts. They are also at greater risk of accidents during their commute home. These data illustrate how MF compromises not only individual safety but also collective safety, particularly in critical sectors [6].

Despite its importance, measuring MF faces challenges, especially due to the invasive nature of some available methods. Physiological measurements, which use biological signals, stand out for their high precision in detecting MF

[7]. On the other hand, subjective and behavioral approaches rely on analytical assessments and self-reports for evaluation [8–10]

Among the advances in this area, machine learning (ML) algorithms have shown great potential in identifying behavioral and physiological patterns, enabling the determination of whether a person is in a state of MF. Key methods for collecting electrophysiological data include electroencephalogram (EEG) and electrocardiogram (ECG). ECG, in particular, is gaining relevance as a less invasive alternative [11], offering high resistance to noise [12] and the ability to provide variables such as heart rate variability (HRV), which is strongly associated with MF states [11, 13].

Several studies have explored the use of ML algorithms to detect MF based on HRV data, among which the work of Matuz et al. stands out as a key source of inspiration and the foundation for data acquisition in our research. This study, along with others [1, 14], employed ML models to predict MF using HRV data, taking into account the variability across different cognitive tasks, an aspect previously underexplored, which enabled better model generalization and greater practical applicability. Matuz et al. found that algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM) and CatBoost regression were effective in classifying and predicting fatigue severity, using predictors such as pre-task fatigue, sex, task duration, and HRV indices. Furthermore, classifiers trained on ECG data collected during task execution outperformed those trained on resting-state data, suggesting that analysis in active contexts is more relevant. Longer data collection windows were also associated with more accurate predictions [15].

Most ML studies still rely on passive learning (PL) strategies, in which models are trained using fully labeled datasets. While effective, this approach requires high computational cost and significant processing time. In contrast, this study adopts active learning (AL) as the reference method. Unlike traditional supervised learning, which uses a fixed labeled dataset, AL strategically selects the most informative data points for labeling, thereby optimizing the training process. The method begins with a small labeled subset and a larger unlabeled pool. Through queries to an oracle (e.g., a human expert), the algorithm identifies which unlabeled samples are most valuable for improving the model. These selected samples are then labeled and iteratively added to the training set. This process reduces the overall labeling effort while maintaining or even enhancing

III. METHODS

model performance. Additionally, AL tends to achieve greater efficiency and accuracy compared to PL approaches, making it particularly suitable for continuous and incremental long-term learning scenarios [16].

In the study of Faria, Bruno, et al., the application of AL algorithms for heart attack prediction is investigated. The study highlights the importance of query strategies, such as entropy sampling and least confidence, and examines the impact of batch size on model efficiency. The authors demonstrate that smaller batch sizes can significantly reduce the number of samples required, achieving 80% accuracy. This work underscores the relevance of AL in scenarios where data labeling is a limited resource, reinforcing the applicability of the technique in the context of the present study [17].

Although our research builds upon the work of Matuz et al., including their publicly available code and datasets, our primary objective is to advance MF detection by applying the AL technique using the Query by Committee (QBC) strategy. This approach involves training multiple models on the same subset of data and analyzing their predictive disagreements to identify the most informative instances for labeling [18]. To this end, we employ the SVM classifier identified in the referenced study as the most effective method to evaluate whether comparable or improved results can be achieved using significantly smaller labeled datasets [15].

We experiment with batch sizes of 20, 40, and 60, combined with time windows of 5, 4, and 3 minutes, respectively, applied to HRV indices collected during cognitive tasks and rest periods. This setup allows us to assess the impact of reduced labeled data volumes on model accuracy and efficiency. Therefore, this study aims to compare the performance of active versus passive learning strategies in MF detection, seeking to optimize model performance while minimizing labeling effort and computational cost.

The next section we describe the materials. Section 3 presents the methods, while Section 4 presents the results. Section 5 provides the discussion. Finally, Section 6 the conclusions.

II. MATERIALS

The dataset employed in this study is the same as that used by Matuz et al. It originates from a combination of three controlled experiments designed to induce fatigue states through the application of various cognitive tasks. The dataset comprises 82 samples and 20 attributes related to HRV, which were selected based on their relevance in previous fatigue detection studies. The original study used data collected during both effortful tasks and resting moments. For additional details on the dataset, refer to the original article [15].

The implementation of the proposed technique leveraged the Scikit-learn framework, a comprehensive library that provides robust tools for data preprocessing and a wide array of ML algorithms. Additionally, the modAL library was utilized for its modular AL capabilities, allowing for the efficient creation of workflows and extensive customization options.

The methodology of this study is grounded in the application of AL techniques for fatigue classification using the aforementioned dataset. The primary objective was to compare active and PL approaches by adapting the algorithm logic from the original study and employing the SVM model, which demonstrated superior performance in prior analyses.

To maintain the study's focus on comparative analysis, only time windows of 3, 4, and 5 minutes were considered. This decision was made to evaluate the model's performance on reduced datasets while ensuring methodological consistency.

A. Active Learning Strategy

The AL approach employed the QBC strategy, wherein sample selection was guided by the maximum disagreement among a committee of models, which included Random Forest, SVM, and KNN. These committee models were parameterized based on the settings from the original article to optimize fatigue detection. This strategy aimed to maximize the informational value of the labeled samples, thereby minimizing the volume of labeled data required for effective model training.

The dataset was divided into a 70:30 split, with 70% of the data allocated for training and 30% for testing the model. This ratio is consistent with common practices found in the literature for datasets of a similar size [19]. After this, the training dataset was divided into labeled and unlabeled subsets. The unlabeled data were organized into three batches, with sizes of 20 (13%), 40 (26%), and 60 (39%) samples, which were selected randomly. For each batch, the committee used the maximum disagreement criterion to identify the most discrepant samples. Then, 25% of the batch was labeled by the "oracle" and added to the labeled dataset. This iterative process is detailed in Algorithm 1.

B. Evaluation

The model's performance was evaluated using several performance metrics, including accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and the Area Under the Curve (AUC). Accuracy indicates the proportion of correct predictions relative to the total cases evaluated, providing an overall view of the model's performance. Sensitivity (or true positive rate) measures the model's ability to correctly identify positive cases, i.e., those where fatigue was correctly classified. Specificity (or true negative rate) evaluates the model's ability to correctly recognize negative cases, i.e., when there is no fatigue. Finally, the AUC provides a comprehensive view of the model's ability to discriminate between classes, with values close to 1 indicating good performance, while values close to 0.5 suggest random classification.

In addition to these metrics, the most selected features in each iteration were also analyzed, following the same approach as in the original algorithm. Together, these metrics and feature analyses allow for a detailed evaluation of the impact of active and passive learning approaches on fatigue classification.

Algorithm 1: Active Learning

Input: Dataset filenames, parameters**Output:** CSV files with SVM results and feature importances

```
1 for each filename in dataset do
2   for each iteration in [1, iterations] do
3     Active Learning:
4     Split training set into labeled and unlabeled
       subsets;
5     Initialize committee with Random Forest,
       SVM, and KNN models;
6     Select most discrepant samples using
       maximum disagreement;
7     Add selected samples to the labeled set;
8     Train an SVM model using Grid Search with
       Cross-Validation;
9     Evaluate SVM using metrics (accuracy,
       ROC-AUC, sensitivity, specificity);
10    Save results to the SVM results table;
11  Save SVM results to a CSV file;
12  Compute statistics (mean, std, frequency) for
       feature importances;
13  Save feature importance statistics to a CSV file;
```

IV. RESULTS

In a similar manner to the baseline study, both the committee and the SVM classifier were trained using HRV data to classify fatigue and non-fatigue states. Prior to this, a feature selection process was applied, which contributed to the identification of the most relevant features for classification. This procedure was carried out as described in the baseline study, but the results obtained differ and are presented in Table 1. In it, the three most relevant features for each process are highlighted, separated by data type and time intervals in minutes.

TABLE 1. The three most important features for each processing step.

Dataset	Feature	Mean importance
5-min Window		
Task	VLF	0.220
	LF	0.167
	SDNN	0.134
Resting	VLF	0.188
	TP	0.0985
	Mean RR	0.0949
	4-min Window	
Task	VLF	0.220
	SD2	0.184
	TP	0.086
Resting	Min HR	0.196
	VLF	0.125
	SD2	0.101
3-min Window		
Task	SD2	0.232
	VLF	0.187
	SDNN	0.137
Resting	VLF	0.135
	Min HR	0.102
	SDNN	0.097

After the selection of relevant features, AL was performed and applied to an SVM model, which was responsible for classifying the data. The model's performance was evaluated for different batch sizes (20, 40, and 60) and time intervals of 3, 4, and 5 minutes. In this regard, the performance is summarized in Tables 2 and 3, which present the mean values of AUC, accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity, all accompanied by 95% confidence intervals.

Through Tables 2 and 3, it can be observed that the performances achieved across different batch sizes and time intervals, both for task and resting data, were similar. However, it is noticeable that with the increase in the number of unlabeled batches used in AL meaning fewer data available for training the SVM model there was a decrease in the mean values of most metrics. Additionally, it was observed that the prediction was slightly better for data obtained from the task experiment, showing higher mean values compared to the resting data, indicating a better characterization of fatigue. Another relevant point concerns the time windows, where longer windows, containing more information, outperformed shorter windows, highlighting the influence of this factor on performance.

Some of these conclusions can be observed in Figures 1, 2, and 3, which provide a visual comparison of the processes through the Mean AUC, highlighting the similarity in performance with different batch sizes and time windows, while also emphasizing the discrepancy between the performances of the task and resting data. Among these, the best performance in characterizing fatigue through the SVM model during the task was achieved with a 5-minute time window and a batch size of 20, reaching an AUC of 0.837 and an accuracy of 75%, using the VLF, LF, and SDNN features. Additionally, it achieved a sensitivity of 74% and a specificity of 77%.

The processing with a batch size of 20 and a 5-minute time window also achieved the best performance with resting data, reaching an AUC of 0.728 and an accuracy of 69%, using the VLF, TP, and Mean RR features. Additionally, it attained a sensitivity of 74% and a specificity of 77%.

IV. DISCUSSION

This work was developed with the aim of applying AL to the model that showed the best results in detecting the fatigue state, as proposed by Matuz et al. This method evaluated several classifiers, including SVM, KNN, Random Forest, and CatBoost, highlighting SVM as the best performing one. The analyzed data were obtained from HRV indices associated with different levels of fatigue, resulting from prolonged performance of highly exhaustive cognitive tasks. In this context, AL was applied using the same dataset and original model, investigating the model's performance when working with reduced datasets, where part of the data was selected by a committee of classifiers [15].

After obtaining average AUC indices ranging from 0.692 to 0.837 and average accuracies between 64% and 75%, a significant proximity to the values reported by the reference study was observed, which reported AUC scores ranging from 0.685 to 0.841 and balanced accuracies between 68% and 76%. This similarity is a satisfactory result, as it

TABLE 2. Evaluation metrics for different time windows and batch sizes for the task.

Time window	Number of batch	Mean AUC (95% CI)	Mean accuracy (95% CI)	Mean sensitivity (95% CI)	Mean specificity (95% CI)
5-min	20	0.837(0.826,0.848)	0.754(0.743,0.766)	0.740(0.722,0.760)	0.768(0.751,0.786)
	40	0.823(0.810,0.835)	0.748(0.736,0.760)	0.735(0.713,0.757)	0.761(0.743,0.778)
	60	0.819(0.807,0.831)	0.737(0.725,0.750)	0.730(0.710,0.750)	0.744(0.722,0.765)
4-min	20	0.831(0.819,0.843)	0.743(0.731,0.755)	0.704(0.687,0.720)	0.783(0.765,0.801)
	40	0.820(0.808,0.832)	0.743(0.730,0.756)	0.718(0.698,0.738)	0.768(0.747,0.788)
	60	0.814(0.800,0.828)	0.736(0.722,0.750)	0.713(0.689,0.736)	0.759(0.736,0.782)
3-min	20	0.808(0.793,0.822)	0.731(0.718,0.744)	0.706(0.687,0.725)	0.756(0.737,0.775)
	40	0.809(0.796,0.822)	0.734(0.722,0.747)	0.708(0.687,0.728)	0.761(0.741,0.780)
	60	0.800(0.787,0.814)	0.721(0.708,0.734)	0.695(0.675,0.715)	0.746(0.725,0.767)

TABLE 3. Evaluation metrics for different time windows and batch sizes for the resting.

Time window	Number of batch	Mean AUC (95% CI)	Mean accuracy (95% CI)	Mean sensitivity (95% CI)	Mean specificity (95% CI)
5-min	20	0.728(0.711,0.745)	0.686(0.672,0.701)	0.707(0.686,0.727)	0.666(0.640,0.691)
	40	0.717(0.698,0.735)	0.670(0.654,0.685)	0.702(0.678,0.725)	0.637(0.611,0.662)
	60	0.699(0.677,0.721)	0.650(0.632,0.668)	0.642(0.610,0.674)	0.657(0.629,0.686)
4-min	20	0.727(0.710,0.744)	0.680(0.664,0.695)	0.676(0.654,0.698)	0.684(0.662,0.706)
	40	0.727(0.711,0.743)	0.670(0.654,0.687)	0.661(0.634,0.688)	0.679(0.653,0.705)
	60	0.716(0.700,0.732)	0.664(0.650,0.678)	0.669(0.640,0.697)	0.659(0.628,0.689)
3-min	20	0.714(0.699,0.729)	0.665(0.651,0.678)	0.636(0.613,0.659)	0.694(0.674,0.713)
	40	0.719(0.706,0.732)	0.667(0.655,0.680)	0.637(0.615,0.659)	0.696(0.672,0.720)
	60	0.692(0.674,0.709)	0.644(0.630,0.660)	0.638(0.607,0.670)	0.650(0.614,0.686)

Fig. 1. Mean AUC for batches of 20

Fig. 3. Mean AUC for batches of 60

Fig. 2. Mean AUC for batches of 40

indicates that AL fulfilled its role by selecting the most relevant data for model training, reducing the need for a large volume of labeled data without significantly compromising performance. Furthermore, this proximity reinforces the effectiveness of the QBC in identifying informative samples, optimizing the classification process. These findings also highlight the feasibility of the method in scenarios with limited resources for data labeling. [15].

The method applied in this work to assess the effectiveness of AL consisted of varying the number of batches of unlabeled samples that were submitted to the model committee. This approach, in turn, also influenced the number of samples labeled by the committee and used for training the SVM model, ranging from 13% to 39% of the total training data. From this variation, it was observed that the predictive power was higher when the models were

trained with larger datasets, i.e., with smaller unlabeled batches, as in the case of the batch of 20 samples. These results demonstrate that, although predictive power decreases when models are trained with smaller datasets, AL mitigates this difference by prioritizing the selection of more informative and relevant samples for training.

Another important finding was the observation that, as in the reference study, predictive power was significantly higher when using data related to tasks, compared to HRV data collected during rest. This result reinforces the conclusion of the reference study that resting ECG recordings may be more susceptible to individual differences, such as mood fluctuations or anxiety levels, which are reflected in cardiac activity and hinder effective learning by the models. Additionally, longer time windows demonstrated superior results, indicating that longer recording periods provide more reliable and detailed information, which contributes to better predictive performance. Specifically, the 5-minute window stood out as the most effective [15].

Finally, among the different factors adjusted in each processing, such as batch number, window size, and type of data collected, the best predictive performance was achieved with the 5-minute window and data collected during task execution. This process resulted in an AUC score of 0.837 and an accuracy of 75%. Although these results also represent the best values observed in the reference study, in this work, they were achieved using a reduced number of samples. In particular, by removing approximately 13% of the total training dataset when working with batches of size 20, the model was able to maintain similar predictive performance. This reinforces the effectiveness of AL selecting the most informative samples, optimizing training even with a smaller volume of labeled data [15].

V. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the application of AL, using the QBC strategy, for the detection of MF based on HRV data. The approach was implemented on the SVM model, which showed the best predictive performance among the models evaluated by Matuz et al. [15]. To ensure a consistent comparison, the same dataset, feature selection model, and acquisition and evaluation protocols were used. The central goal was to verify whether AL with the QBC strategy could achieve results comparable to or better than those of the reference study, even when employing smaller datasets, previously selected informatively by the model committee.

In this study, batches of sizes 20, 40, and 60 were used to evaluate the impact of the number of unlabeled samples selected in each iteration of AL on the performance of the SVM model. The batch of size 20 yielded the best predictive results, indicating that smaller datasets of unlabeled samples, carefully selected by the model committee, are more effective for training the model. Although the batches of 40 and 60 also produced good results, their performance was slightly inferior, possibly due to applying fewer samples to the training process, despite selecting more samples through the committee.

Through this data, it was observed that the results demonstrated that AL was effective in reducing the need for labeled data without significantly compromising the model's

predictive performance. The model trained with the proposed approach yielded predictions consistent with those of the reference study, highlighting that active learning can identify more informative and relevant samples for training while maintaining the quality of the model.

Furthermore, one of the main advantages of AL lies in its ability to enable incremental and continuous learning, whereby the model can be progressively updated as new samples are selected and labeled, without the need to retrain the model from scratch. Additionally, it was found that longer time windows, particularly the 5-minute windows, and data collected during the execution of cognitive tasks were more representative for fatigue detection. This is in comparison to data collected during rest and smaller time windows, corroborating the findings of the reference study. These results highlight the relevance of longer collection periods and active contexts for a more accurate assessment of the state of fatigue.

Finally, the optimal configuration identified in this study combined batch sizes of 20, 5-minute time windows, and data collected during cognitive tasks. This resulted in an AUC score of 0.837 and an accuracy of 75%, which are comparable to the results reported by Matuz et al. [15]. These findings reinforce the feasibility of employing active learning in scenarios with limited resources for data labeling and pave the way for future research on the use of this approach in real-world applications particularly where adaptive, scalable, and progressive learning systems are required.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. A. Boksem and M. Tops, "Mental fatigue: costs and benefits," *Brain research reviews*, vol. 59, no. 1, pp. 125–139, 2008.
- [2] D. van der Linden, M. Frese, and T. F. Meijman, "Mental fatigue and the control of cognitive processes: effects on perseveration and planning," *Acta Psychologica*, vol. 113, no. 1, pp. 45–65, 2003.
- [3] G. R. J. Hockey, "A motivational control theory of cognitive fatigue," pp. 167–187, 2011.
- [4] S. Lerman, E. Eskin, D. Flower, E. George, B. Gerson, N. Hartenbaum, S. Hursh, M. Moore-Ede, A. C. of Occupational, and E. M. P. T. F. on Fatigue Risk Management, "Fatigue risk management in the workplace," *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 231–258, 2012.
- [5] S. Lockley, L. Barger, N. Ayas, J. Rothschild, C. Czeisler, C. Landrigan, H. Harvard Work Hours, and S. Group, "Effects of health care provider work hours and sleep deprivation on safety and performance," *Joint Commission Journal on Quality and Patient Safety*, vol. 33, pp. 7–18, Nov 2007.
- [6] D. Ke, "Overwork, stroke, and karoshi-death from overwork," *Acta Neurologica Taiwan*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 54–59, 2012.

- [7] X. Fan, Q. Zhou, Z. Liu, and F. Xie, "Electroencephalogram assessment of mental fatigue in visual search," *Biomedical Materials Engineering*, vol. 26, no. s1, pp. S1455–S1463, 2015.
- [8] C. Goumopoulos and N. Potha, "Mental fatigue detection using a wearable commodity device and machine learning," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, vol. 14, pp. 10103–10121, 2023.
- [9] A. Urrila, P. Stenuit, O. Huhdankoski, M. Kerkhofs, and T. Porkka-Heiskanen, "Psychomotor vigilance task performance during total sleep deprivation in young and postmenopausal women," *Behavioral Brain Research*, vol. 180, no. 1, pp. 42–47, 2007.
- [10] K. Lee, G. Hicks, and G. Nino-Murcia, "Validity and reliability of a scale to assess fatigue," *Psychiatry Research*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 291–298, 1991.
- [11] R. Orsila, M. Virtanen, T. Luukkaala, *et al.*, "Perceived mental stress and reactions in heart rate variability—a pilot study among employees of an electronics company," *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 275–283, 2008.
- [12] S. Murugan, J. Selvaraj, and A. Sahayadhas, "Detection and analysis: driver state with electrocardiogram (ecg)," *Physica Engg. Science Med.*, vol. 43, no. 2, pp. 525–537, 2020.
- [13] S. Duschek, M. Muckenthaler, N. Werner, and G. Del Paso, "Relationships between features of autonomic cardiovascular control and cognitive performance," *Biological Psychology*, vol. 81, no. 2, pp. 110–117, 2009.
- [14] F. Laurent, M. Valderrama, M. Besserve, M. Guillard, J.-P. Lachaux, J. Martinerie, and G. Florence, "Multimodal information improves the rapid detection of mental fatigue," *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 400–408, 2013.
- [15] A. Matuz, D. van der Linden, G. Darnai, and Á. Csathó, "Generalisable machine learning models trained on heart rate variability data to predict mental fatigue," *Scientific Reports*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 20023, 2022.
- [16] E. Mosqueira-Rey, E. Hernández-Pereira, D. Alonso-Ríos, J. Bobes-Bascarán, and Á. Fernández-Leal, "Human-in-the-loop machine learning: a state of the art," *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 3005–3054, 2023.
- [17] B. Faria, D. Perdigoão, J. Brás, and L. Macedo, "The joint role of batch size and query strategy in active learning-based prediction—a case study in the heart attack domain," in *EPIA Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, pp. 464–475, Springer, 2022.
- [18] H. S. Seung, M. Opper, and H. Sompolinsky, "Query by committee," in *Proceedings of the fifth annual workshop on Computational learning theory*, pp. 287–294, 1992.
- [19] Baeldung, "Train-test split ratio: How to decide?," 2021. Accessed: 2025-07-21.